

Voting Mechanism for Trustworthy Localization in Wireless Sensor Networks

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2 ABSTRACT

3 This work aspires to provide a trustworthy solution for target localization in adverse environments,
4 where malicious nodes, capable of manipulating distance measurements (i.e., performing spoofing
5 attacks), are present, thus hindering accurate localization. Besides localization, its other goal is
6 to identify (detect) which of the nodes participating in the process are malicious. This problem
7 becomes extremely important with the forthcoming expansion of IoT and smart cities applications,
8 that depend on accurate localization, and the presence of malicious attackers can represent
9 serious security threats if not taken into consideration. This is the case with most existing
10 localization systems which makes them highly vulnerable to spoofing attacks. In addition, existing
11 methods that are intended for adversarial settings consider very specific settings or require
12 additional knowledge about the system model, making them only partially secure. Therefore,
13 this work proposes a novel voting scheme based on clustering and weighted central mass to
14 securely solve the localization problem and detect attackers. The proposed solution has two
15 main phases: 1) Choosing a cluster of suitable points of interest by taking advantage of the
16 problem geometry to assigning votes in order to localize the target, and 2) Attacker detection by
17 exploiting the location estimate and basic statistics. The proposed method is assessed in terms
18 of localization accuracy, success in attacker detection, and computational complexity in different
19 settings. Computer simulations and real-world experiments corroborate the effectiveness of the
20 proposed scheme compared to state-of-the-art methods, showing that it can accomplish an error
21 reduction of 30 % and is capable of achieving almost perfect attacker detection rate when the
22 ratio between attacker intensity and noise standard deviation is significant.

23 **Keywords:** Secure localization, Voting scheme (VS), Clustering, Received signal strength (RSS), Weighted central mass (WCM),
24 Spoofing attacks.

1 INTRODUCTION

25 Recently, wireless sensor networks (WSNs) have attracted much interest of the scientific community,
26 partially due to their ability to work in harsh environments, ease and low costs of implementation Tomic
27 et al. (2018); Matos-Carvalho et al. (2021), and wide variety of applications Oigbochie et al. (2021); Qiang
28 (2014). From the localization perspective, generally, WSNs are composed of two distinct types of nodes: 1)
29 anchor nodes, whose locations are known and serve as reference points in the localization process and 2)
30 target nodes, whose locations are unknown and one desires to determine them. Naturally, it is expected that
31 nodes are capable to communicate with each other in order to execute the localization task. In this work, a
32 non-cooperative network, where targets are only allowed to communicate with anchors, is considered.

33 In most applications, data acquired by sensors are only useful if they can be associated with the respective
34 physical location Bazzi et al. (2016a), Shi and Yang (2024). However, most existing localization systems
35 overlook possible security threats Tomic and Beko (2020); Coluccia and Fascista (2018), Bazzi et al.
36 (2016b), Bazzi et al. (2018). Therefore, if these systems are exposed to malicious attacks, they can result in
37 catastrophic outcomes (e.g., failure in a self-driving car collision system, change in drone trajectory, etc.).
38 Mainly for this reason, localization systems should be developed for potentially adversarial environments,
39 where a malicious (or damaged) sensor can produce false distance measurements (spoofing attacks) to
40 manipulate the localization process.

41 Perhaps the easiest and most common way of localization is to equip sensors with global positioning
42 system (GPS) receivers. However, this solution has several undesirable consequences, such as increased
43 implementation costs and infeasibility in some environments (e.g., indoor, urban areas, forests, etc.). In
44 addition, from the security point of view, GPS is considered a civilian localization system (e.g., uses
45 unencrypted signals); thus, it is not very difficult to manipulate (spooft) it. Although there are different
46 types of attacks in WSNs nowadays, this work focuses its attention on spoofing attacks specifically due to
47 their close relationship with distance measurements (proximity). These attacks include forging distance
48 measurements (either by reducing or enlarging them) that can be performed in various non-cryptographic
49 ways, meaning that no infraction of upper-layer security protocols for carrying out these attacks is at risk
50 (for instance, an attacker can add a physical obstacle between two nodes or change node's transmit power
51 without informing its neighbours). Moreover, these attacks (including GPS spoofing) come at a relatively
52 low cost, but can cause severe problems in many systems Kugler (2017). Since spoofing attacks are closely
53 related with distance they have real-world impact and are used in car thefts, executions of unauthorized
54 payments and manipulation of navigation Singh et al. (2019).

55 1.1 Related Work

56 Secure localization in WSNs has attracted interest in the scientific literature Li et al. (2005); Liu et al.
57 (2007); Garg et al. (2012); Liu et al. (2019); Li et al. (2021); Beko and Tomic (2021); Tomic and Beko
58 (2022); Mukhopadhyay et al. (2021); Tomic and Beko (2024a,b). Still, there is no uniquely accepted
59 solution and there is room for improvement in all aspects (localization accuracy, detection rates and
60 complexity).

61 In Li et al. (2005), two secure localization solutions were explored: least median of squares (LMS) and
62 radio frequency (RF) fingerprinting. LMS selects the subset of anchors with the least median residues,
63 while RF fingerprinting employs a median-based distance metric. The work in Liu et al. (2007) introduced
64 attack-resistant minimum mean square estimation (ARMMSE) and a voting scheme (VS). ARMMSE
65 detects and removes malicious anchors based on inconsistencies, whereas VS assigns votes to grid cells

66 based on distance measurements, identifying the target's likely location. An iterative algorithm using
67 gradient descent was proposed in Garg et al. (2012) for both uncoordinated and coordinated attacks.
68 Malicious anchors were identified by their higher residues and excluded from the localization process.
69 In Liu et al. (2019), a density-based spatial clustering method classified location points as normal or
70 abnormal, followed by a sequential probability ratio test to authenticate anchors using received signal
71 strength (RSS) and time of arrival (TOA) data. The study in Li et al. (2021) addressed secure localization
72 and velocity estimation in mobile WSNs with malicious anchors, using a maximum a posteriori (MAP)
73 estimator solved via variational message passing. In Beko and Tomic (2021), an initial location estimate
74 was obtained via weighted central mass (WCM), followed by distance-based filtering and a generalized
75 trust region sub-problem (GTRS) solved using a bisection method. This was extended in Tomic and Beko
76 (2022) to a general range-based scenario using a generalized likelihood ratio test (GLRT) and law of
77 cosines (LC). The work in Mukhopadhyay et al. (2021) proposed secure weighted least squares (SWLS) for
78 uncoordinated spoofing attacks and 11-norm (LN-1E) for coordinated attacks. SWLS filters malicious nodes
79 based on estimated noise standard deviation, while LN-1E uses 3D plane fitting and K-means clustering to
80 separate malicious anchors. In Tomic and Beko (2024a), a robust min-max approach was formulated as a
81 second-order cone programming (R-SOCP) problem and a robust GTRS (R-GTRS). Lastly, Tomic and
82 Beko (2024b) introduced an alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM) approach, applying a
83 weighted least squares criterion within a decomposition-coordination iterative scheme.

84 Even though the methods in Li et al. (2005)-Tomic and Beko (2024b) work well in the settings under
85 scrutiny in the respective works, they either require additional knowledge on certain parameters, such as
86 noise power or the maximum magnitude of an attack (e.g., Liu et al. (2007), Liu et al. (2019), Li et al.
87 (2021), Mukhopadhyay et al. (2021), Tomic and Beko (2024a)) and/or convex relaxations/approximations
88 that expand the set of possible solution leading to higher error (e.g., Li et al. (2005), Li et al. (2021)-
89 Tomic and Beko (2024a)) or are executed iteratively (e.g., Garg et al. (2012), Tomic and Beko (2024b)),
90 leaving room for improvement in all aspects (localization accuracy, detection rates and complexity). These
91 limitations could severely deteriorate their performance in scenarios where the required parameters are
92 unknown or imperfectly known, i.e., where problem assumptions do not hold, resulting in the applied
93 relaxations/approximations not being sufficiently tight or lead to burdensome computations that might even
94 raise convergence issues. Furthermore, the majority of the existing works assume knowledge about the type
95 of spoofing attacks (uncoordinated or coordinated) under which the network is beforehand and develop a
96 solution for that specific type of attack. However, it is not possible to acquire such knowledge in practice.
97 Therefore, there are still some challenges to address and room for improvement in all main aspects of the
98 considered problem.

99 1.2 Main Contributions of the Current Work

100 This work presents a geometric approach to compute intersection points between pairs of anchors and
101 obtain an estimate of the target's location through a VS and WCM, which is then exploited to detect
102 attackers based on confidence intervals (CIs). Unlike Liu et al. (2007); Garg et al. (2012); Beko and Tomic
103 (2021); Tomic and Beko (2022); Mukhopadhyay et al. (2021), the proposed algorithm does not make hard
104 (binary) detection decisions, but assigns beliefs (votes) to each intersection point, leveraging information
105 from malicious anchors when attack intensity is low. Besides, mistakenly removing a genuine anchor can
106 severely degrade the localization accuracy, leading to severe and potentially lethal consequences in real life,
107 such as collisions of autonomous vehicles with obstacles, another vehicles or infrastructure, tardy arrival at
108 the desired location in the case of an emergency event, like wildfire and organ transplantation and similar.
109 The highest-voted points are converted into probabilities and used as WCM weights for location estimation.

110 Attack intensities are assessed per link using a maximum likelihood (ML) criterion, with attacker detection
 111 based on CIs at a predefined level. Due to its geometric nature, the method is adaptable to any range-based
 112 measurement. The primary goal is to advance secure localization beyond traditional systems, ensuring
 113 reliable malicious node detection and accurate target positioning. The main contributions of this work are
 114 threefold and are summarized in the following:

- 115 • Design of a novel solution for target localization in randomly deployed sensor network in the presence
 116 of (uncoordinated and coordinated) spoofing attacks based on a new VS. The proposed localization
 117 estimator is a single-iteration scheme based on simple geometry, where points of interest extracted
 118 from the system model are clustered together and appraised by assigning votes to reach a set of the
 119 most trustworthy points. This set of points is then used to get an estimate on the target's location
 120 through WCM.
- 121 • Unlike the existing methods that make a *hard* binary decision, the current work converts votes into
 122 probabilities and makes a *soft* detection decision, i.e., it makes use of all anchors and gradually builds
 123 its confidence regarding which anchors might be malicious and which not, not excluding any anchor in
 124 the process.
- 125 • Proposal of a novel attacker detection scheme based on CIs. By exploiting the location estimate,
 126 estimates of the attack intensities and the genuine (non-malicious) measurement values are acquired
 127 and used to evaluate if a reported measurement falls outside a CI of one (estimated) standard deviation
 128 from its *genuine* doublet.
- 129 • The proposed solution not only matches, but outperforms more complex state-of-the-art solutions
 130 for high attack intensities. Thus, the proposed method sets the best achievable results reported in the
 131 literature thus far, both in terms of localization and detection performance.
- 132 • Lastly, both computer simulations and real-world experimental measurements are employed to validate
 133 the performance of the proposed solution.

134 Throughout the work, uppercase bold type, lowercase bold type, and regular type of fonts are used to
 135 denote matrices, vectors, and scalars, respectively. \mathbb{R}^n denotes the n -dimensional real Euclidean space.
 136 Symbol $(\bullet)^T$ represent the transpose operator, while $\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$ and $proj_S(\mathbf{p})$ denote the binomial
 137 coefficients and the projection of the point \mathbf{p} onto the set S , respectively. The normal (Gaussian) distribution
 138 with mean μ and variance σ^2 is denoted by $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma^2)$. The N -dimensional identity matrix is denoted by
 139 \mathbf{I}_N and the $M \times N$ matrix of all zeros by $\mathbf{0}_{M \times N}$ (if no ambiguity can occur, subscripts are omitted). $\|\mathbf{x}\|$
 140 denotes the vector norm defined by $\|\mathbf{x}\| = \sqrt{\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{x}}$, where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a column vector. The i -th column of
 141 the matrix \mathbf{M} is denoted by \mathbf{M}_i and an estimate of a parameter \mathbf{x} with $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$.

142 The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 defines the problem, while Section 3 details
 143 the proposed solution. Section 4 presents performance comparisons, and Section 5 summarizes the key
 144 findings.

2 PROBLEM FORMULATION

145 Let us consider a 2-dimensional, non-cooperative and static WSN, where a single target, whose true
 146 location is unknown and denoted by \mathbf{x} , is located at a time by the help of a set of anchors whose true
 147 locations are known and denoted by $\mathbf{a}_i, i = 1, \dots, N$. Some of the anchors are assumed malicious and try
 148 to disrupt the location process by manipulating their distance measurements (spoofing attacks). The target
 149 receives radio signals (from which it measures the RSS values) from the anchors. Note that in this work the

150 measurement acquisition is assumed practically instantaneous; thus, ambient conditions do not change
 151 significantly during the measurement process, having very little to no impact on the deviation of the RSS
 152 measurements. This work considers two types of spoofing attacks: coordinated and uncoordinated.

153 2.1 Uncoordinated Attack

154 In this setting, the genuine anchors have a predefined transmitted power, while the malicious anchors
 155 change the transmitted power arbitrarily without notifying the network. The k -th RSS measurement sample
 156 ($k = 1, \dots, K$) between the target and the i -th anchor can be modeled as

$$P_{i,k} = P_0 - 10\gamma \log_{10} \frac{\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{a}_i\|}{d_0} + \delta_i + n_{i,k} \quad (1)$$

157 where

$$\delta_i = \begin{cases} 0, & i \in \mathcal{H} \\ \delta, & i \in \mathcal{M} \end{cases},$$

158 and \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{H} are, respectively, the set of malicious and honest nodes, P_0 is the RSS at a short reference
 159 distance d_0 (for simplicity referred to as the transmitted power), γ is the path loss exponent (PLE)
 160 representing the decay of the signal strength with distance, $n_{i,k}$ is the noise term modeled as $n_{i,k} \sim$
 161 $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{i,k}^2)$, and $\delta_i \in \mathbb{R}$ is the intensity of the spoofing attack of the i -th anchor. Note that in this work the
 162 measurement acquisition is assumed practically instantaneous; thus, ambient conditions do not change
 163 significantly during the measurement process, having very little to no impact on the deviation of the RSS
 164 measurements.

165 Note that, in contrast to Beko and Tomic (2021), where malicious anchors could only enlarge their
 166 distance measurements, in this work it is assumed that the attackers can either reduce or enlarge distance
 167 measurements. For simplicity, it is assumed that the variance of all measurements is equal (for every link
 168 and sample), i.e., for $\sigma_{i,k}^2 = \sigma^2$, $i = 1, \dots, N$ and $k = 1, \dots, K$. Moreover, to easier combat outliers and also
 169 for the sake of notation simplicity and without loss of generality, the median of all K RSS measurements
 170 in (1) from the i -th anchor (P_i) is used in the following derivations.

171 Figure 1a shows an uncoordinated attack, where two (represented by red squares) of the five anchors are
 172 malicious and report, independently, false distance measurements, aggravating the localization process.
 173 In the concrete case, both malicious anchors reduced their measurements independently from each other,
 174 resulting in two intersection points of the red dashed circles to be relatively remote from the main cluster
 175 of the intersection points and thus, from the true target location.

176 2.2 Coordinated Attack

177 In coordinated attacks the malicious anchors communicate with each other to agree on a (false) location
 178 for the target. The idea is to make the network believe that the target is at a different location than it actually
 179 is. Similar to Mukhopadhyay et al. (2021), the coordinated attack can be modeled as

$$P_{i,k} = \begin{cases} P_0 - 10\gamma \log_{10} \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{a}_i\|}{d_0} \right) + n_{i,k} & i \in \mathcal{H} \\ P_0 - 10\gamma \log_{10} \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{x}_{att} - \mathbf{a}_i\|}{d_0} \right) + n_{i,k} & i \in \mathcal{M}, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1a. Uncoordinated attack

Figure 1b. Coordinated attack

Figure 1. Illustration of different types of spoofing attacks: the red dashed and black solid circles respectively denote malicious and genuine measurements (converted into distance).

180 where x_{att} is the false location that the attackers agree upon.

181 Figure 1b shows an example of a coordinated attack, where two malicious anchors (represented by a red
182 square) attempt to make the network think that the location of the target is the one represented by a blue
183 triangle (x_{att}) instead of the real target position represented by a blue cross (x).

184 Note that (2) is a special case of (1), having $\delta_i = 10\gamma \log_{10} \frac{\|x - a_i\|}{\|x_{att} - a_i\|}$. Hence, this work adopts (1) as the
185 general model for both types of spoofing attacks. From it, the probability density function of x parametrized
186 by the median RSS observation at the i -th anchor P_i is given by

$$f(x; P_i) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{\left(P_i - P_0 + 10\gamma \log_{10} \left(\frac{\|x - a_i\|}{d_0} \right) - \delta_i \right)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right\}, \quad (3)$$

187 where $\exp\{\bullet\}$ denotes the exponential function. Minimizing (3) leads to the ML estimator Kay (1993).
188 However, the ML estimator is non-convex and therefore difficult to tackle directly. In this work, a VS
189 algorithm is introduced to estimate the target's location instead.

3 THE PROPOSED APPROACH FOR THE SECURE LOCALIZATION PROBLEM

190 This section describes the derivation of the proposed algorithm for secure localization. It is organized into
191 three parts: 1) a preliminary part, where points of interest are determined, and two main parts in which
192 2) the proposed localization estimator is described in detail, and 3) the proposed detection procedure to
193 identify attackers is introduced.

194 **3.1 Determining Points of Interest**

195 At the beginning, all anchors are treated as honest. Hence, the set of malicious nodes is initialized as
 196 $\mathcal{M} = \emptyset$, whereas the set of honest nodes is $\mathcal{H} = \{i : 1 \leq i \leq N\}$. Afterwards, one can construct circles, c_i ,
 197 centered at the known locations of the anchors and radii equivalent to the distance estimate, $\hat{d}_i = d_0 10^{\frac{P_0 - P_i}{10\gamma}}$,
 198 obtained from (1), of the respective anchor (the reader is referred to Fig. 2a). The intersection points
 199 between all pairs of circles are used as points of interest for the voting scheme. The intersection points
 200 between a pair of circles (given that they exist) can be calculated Tomic and Beko (2022) as follows

$$\mathbf{q}'_{ij} = \mathbf{q}_0 + \mathbf{t} \text{ and } \mathbf{q}''_{ij} = \mathbf{q}_0 - \mathbf{t}, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, N-1, j = i+1, \dots, N, \quad (4)$$

201 where

$$\mathbf{q}_0 = (\mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{a}_i) \frac{\hat{d}_i^2 - \hat{d}_j^2}{2\|\mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{a}_i\|^2} + \frac{\mathbf{a}_i + \mathbf{a}_j}{2},$$

202

$$\mathbf{t} = \frac{\sqrt{u}}{2\|\mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{a}_i\|^2} \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{a}_i), \mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

203 with

$$u = \left((\hat{d}_i + \hat{d}_j)^2 - \|\mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{a}_i\|^2 \right) \left(\|\mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{a}_i\|^2 - (\hat{d}_j - \hat{d}_i)^2 \right),$$

204 according to Fig. 2a. However, due to the presence of noise and possibly malicious/faulty nodes, a pair of
 205 circles might not intersect (the reader is referred to Fig. 2b). In this case, the tuple set of anchors without
 206 intersection is defined as $\mathcal{C} = \{(i, j) : c_i \cap c_j = \emptyset\}$, where the notation $c_i \cap c_j = \emptyset$ is used to denote that
 207 the circles corresponding to the i -th and j -th anchors do not intersect. In that case, one can draw a line that
 208 passes through the respective pair of anchors, and compute the intersections between the circles and the
 209 drawn line as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{q}_{i,1} &= \mathbf{a}_0 + \left[(\mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{a}_0)^T \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \sqrt{[(\mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{a}_0)^T \hat{\mathbf{b}}]^2 - (\mathbf{a}_0^T \mathbf{a}_0 + \mathbf{a}_i^T \mathbf{a}_i - d_i - 2\mathbf{a}_0^T \mathbf{a}_i)} \right], \\ \mathbf{q}_{i,2} &= \mathbf{a}_0 + \left[(\mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{a}_0)^T \hat{\mathbf{b}} - \sqrt{[(\mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{a}_0)^T \hat{\mathbf{b}}]^2 - (\mathbf{a}_0^T \mathbf{a}_0 + \mathbf{a}_i^T \mathbf{a}_i - d_i - 2\mathbf{a}_0^T \mathbf{a}_i)} \right], \\ \mathbf{q}_{j,1} &= \mathbf{a}_0 + \left[(\mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{a}_0)^T \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \sqrt{[(\mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{a}_0)^T \hat{\mathbf{b}}]^2 - (\mathbf{a}_0^T \mathbf{a}_0 + \mathbf{a}_j^T \mathbf{a}_j - d_j - 2\mathbf{a}_0^T \mathbf{a}_j)} \right], \\ \mathbf{q}_{j,2} &= \mathbf{a}_0 + \left[(\mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{a}_0)^T \hat{\mathbf{b}} - \sqrt{[(\mathbf{a}_j - \mathbf{a}_0)^T \hat{\mathbf{b}}]^2 - (\mathbf{a}_0^T \mathbf{a}_0 + \mathbf{a}_j^T \mathbf{a}_j - d_j - 2\mathbf{a}_0^T \mathbf{a}_j)} \right], \end{aligned}$$

210 where $\mathbf{a}_0 = \frac{\mathbf{a}_i + \mathbf{a}_j}{2}$ is the position vector of the line, and $\hat{\mathbf{b}} = \frac{(\mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{a}_j)}{\|\mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{a}_j\|}$ is the unit vector that describes the
 211 line's direction. Afterwards, the intersection points to be used in the voting-scheme, \mathbf{q}'_{ij} , \mathbf{q}''_{ij} , are obtained
 212 as the middle of the intersection points between the line and the circles at both ends, according to

$$\mathbf{q}'_{ij} = \frac{\mathbf{q}_{i,1} + \mathbf{q}_{j,1}}{2}, \quad \mathbf{q}''_{ij} = \frac{\mathbf{q}_{i,2} + \mathbf{q}_{j,2}}{2} \quad (5)$$

213 The forged intersection points are required for the proposed algorithm in scenarios where the number of
 214 anchors is scarce and/or the genuine intersection points are in insufficient number. This idea has already

Figure 2a. True intersections between a pair of anchors **Figure 2b.** Forged intersections between a pair of anchors

Figure 2. Illustration of finding/forging circles' intersections.

215 been implemented in Tomic and Beko (2022), and the reasoning behind it is that when a pair of anchors is
 216 genuine, the intersection points would lay in the vicinity of the drawn line, making these forged intersection
 217 points a reasonable approximation of the real ones.

218 3.2 The Proposed Voting-based Scheme for Target Localization

219 The voting scheme is a process to cluster and assign votes to the intersection points based on some criterion
 220 (for instance, their physical proximity). The main idea is to assign a value (vote) to each intersection point
 221 in order to find the most trustworthy ones. It is important to highlight that the localization process is done
 222 for a specific instant in time, therefore, past information of the network is not used to aid the voting-scheme.
 223 For the sake of simplicity, let us define the matrix $\mathbf{Q} = [q'_{ij} \ q''_{ij}] \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times \binom{N}{2}}$ containing all intersection
 224 points, and the vector $\mathbf{Q}_g \in \mathbb{R}^2$ as the g -th column of \mathbf{Q} . This process iterates all pairs of anchors, and for
 225 each pair a hyperplane is computed as

$$H_{ij} = \{g : \hat{\mathbf{b}}^T \mathbf{Q}_g = \hat{\mathbf{b}}^T \mathbf{a}_0\}, \tag{6}$$

226 which divides the problem space into two half spaces. The intersection points are assigned to the upper half
 227 space, $H_{ij}^{(u)} = \{g : \hat{\mathbf{b}}^T \mathbf{Q}_g > \hat{\mathbf{b}}^T \mathbf{a}_0\}$, or to the lower half space, $H_{ij}^{(l)} = \{g : \hat{\mathbf{b}}^T \mathbf{Q}_g < \hat{\mathbf{b}}^T \mathbf{a}_0\}$, according to
 228 their physical location with respect to the hyperplane. Next, clusters composed of $N - 1$ elements that
 229 are physically the closest to each other in each half space are built: $C_{ij}^{(u)} \subseteq H_{ij}^{(u)}$ as the upper cluster and
 230 $C_{ij}^{(l)} \subseteq H_{ij}^{(l)}$ as the lower cluster. Lastly, votes, v_g , are assigned to the points that belong to a cluster (if
 231 these exist), based on their distance to the hyperplane, see Figure 3. Vote for the g -th intersection point is
 232 calculated as

$$v_g = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N w_g \frac{\text{proj}_{H_{ij}}(\mathbf{Q}_g)}{\sum_{g:g \in C_{ij}^{(u)}} \text{proj}_{H_{ij}}(\mathbf{Q}_g)} + w_g \frac{\text{proj}_{H_{ij}}(\mathbf{Q}_g)}{\sum_{g:g \in C_{ij}^{(l)}} \text{proj}_{H_{ij}}(\mathbf{Q}_g)}, \quad g \in C_{ij}^{(u)} \cup C_{ij}^{(l)} \tag{7}$$

Figure 3. The voting process between two anchors when $N = 4$.

233 where

$$w_g = \begin{cases} \frac{\hat{d}_j}{\hat{d}_i + \hat{d}_j}, & \text{if } g \in H_{ij}^{(u)} \\ \frac{\hat{d}_i}{\hat{d}_i + \hat{d}_j}, & \text{if } g \in H_{ij}^{(l)} \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

234

$$proj_{H_{ij}}(\mathbf{Q}_g) = \|\mathbf{Q}_g - (ee^T \mathbf{Q}_g + (\mathbf{I}_2 - ee^T)\mathbf{a}_0)\| \quad (9)$$

235 with $e = \widehat{T\mathbf{b}}$, \mathbf{I}_2 is the identity matrix of order two, $proj_{H_{ij}}(\mathbf{Q}_g)$ denotes the distance of an intersection
 236 point, \mathbf{Q}_g , to it's respective projection on the hyperplane, and w_g is a weight based on the distances \hat{d}_i and
 237 \hat{d}_j which takes into account the anchor and the point \mathbf{Q}_g .

238 The procedure to compute the votes defined in (7) is explained in the following. For every point of interest
 239 \mathbf{Q}_g , with $g = 1, \dots, \binom{N}{2}$, one considers all combinations of pairs of anchors (i, j) , where $i = 1, \dots, N$ and
 240 $j = i + 1, \dots, N$, and calculates the respective hyperplanes H_{ij} according to (6). Then, each weight w_g
 241 divides a single vote according to the proximity of H_{ij} to \mathbf{a}_i and \mathbf{a}_j , such that more weight is assigned
 242 to the half space containing the anchor closer to the hyperplane (8). A cluster of $N - 1$ points physically
 243 closest to one another, $C_{ij}^{(u)}$ and $C_{ij}^{(l)}$, are formed in each half space. If $g \in C_{ij}^{(u)}$ or $g \in C_{ij}^{(l)}$, distances of
 244 the cluster points to H_{ij} are calculated (9) and converted into weights by dividing the individual distances
 245 with the sum of all distances of the points in the cluster to the hyperplane; otherwise, sum zero and move
 246 on to the next anchor pair. Lastly, these weights are further weighted with w_g and summed up to form
 247 a vote for the g -th point of interest. Hence, the intuition behind the votes defined in (7) is that it assigns
 248 greater weights (belief) to points closer to the hyperplane, since the correct cluster of (genuine) points
 249 should lie in its vicinity.

250 An estimate of the target's location can be obtained by re-ordering the vote vector in a descending fashion,
 251 $\tilde{\mathbf{v}} = [\tilde{v}_h]$, such that $\tilde{v}_1 \geq \tilde{v}_2 \geq \dots \geq \tilde{v}_{\binom{N}{2}}$. The first $N - 1$ votes correspond to the most trustworthy points;
 252 hence, the estimate is obtained by applying the WCM principle for the $N - 1$ (normalized) vote values as

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \sum_{h=1}^{N-1} \tilde{w}_h \mathbf{Q}_h, \quad \text{with } \tilde{w}_h = \frac{\tilde{v}_h}{\sum_{h=1}^{N-1} \tilde{v}_h}. \quad (10)$$

253 3.3 Attack Detection

254 Considering (3), in the case of a malicious anchor, it is intuitive that the attack would shift the probability
 255 distribution according to the attack intensity. This shift of the distribution could cause the mean to fall
 256 outside of a CI. In other words, one could take advantage of it to detect attackers. However, as the attack
 257 intensity is unknown, it can be estimated by exploiting the estimated target location in (10) based on the
 258 ML principle. Similar can be done for the noise standard deviation and the expected (genuine) RSS value
 259 as

$$\hat{\delta}_i = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K P_0 - P_{i,k} - 10\gamma \log_{10} \|\hat{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{a}_i\|}{K}, \quad (11)$$

260

$$\hat{\sigma} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{1}{(K-1)} \sum_{k=1}^K (\alpha_i - \hat{\delta}_i)^2}, \quad (12)$$

$$\hat{P}_i = P_0 - 10\gamma \log_{10} \|\hat{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{a}_i\|, \quad (13)$$

261 with $\alpha_{i,k} = P_{i,k} - P_0 + 10\gamma \log_{10} \|\hat{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{a}_i\|$.

262 It is well known that 68 % of the mass of a normal distribution falls within one standard deviation of the
 263 mean. Thus, if the measured RSS in (1) lays outside of the CI $[\hat{P}_i - \hat{\sigma}, \hat{P}_i + \hat{\sigma}]$, the respective anchor is
 264 classified as malicious, and the set of malicious nodes becomes $\mathcal{M} = \{i : P_i < \hat{P}_i - \hat{\sigma} \vee P_i > \hat{P}_i + \hat{\sigma}\}$.
 265 Notice that the symmetric band $[\hat{P}_i - \hat{\sigma}, \hat{P}_i + \hat{\sigma}]$ used to flag an anchor as malicious might not be the
 266 optimal one, especially for anchors at very different ranges. Still, it effectively serves its intended purpose
 267 and achieves strong performance in practice; thus, its further enhancement is left for future work.

268 Note that, in contrast to Beko and Tomic (2021)-Mukhopadhyay et al. (2021), the malicious node is
 269 possibly exploited in the localization process. This can be advantageous when the $|\delta_i|$ is not high compared
 270 to noise power, and quantity of anchors prevails over quality.

271 The proposed algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1. It should be noted that the proposed algorithm
 272 operates entirely locally at the target using a single network snapshot in time. While the inferred corruption
 273 status of the anchors could be reused by the same target over time (e.g., in tracking or navigation problems)
 274 or shared with other targets in a cooperative setting, such mechanisms fall outside the scope of this work;
 275 thus, no inter-target cooperation or information exchange is assumed or required by the algorithm.

4 PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

276 This section presents a series of numerical results in order to assess the performance of the proposed
 277 solution. It presents analysis based on computational complexity, localization accuracy and success in
 278 detecting malicious attackers, as well as a discussion on the limitations of the proposed scheme. It is thus
 279 organized correspondingly.

280 4.1 Complexity Analysis

281 The complexity analysis is highly relevant for the applicability of the algorithm, especially in real-time
 282 scenarios. Given that B_{\max} and B_{ADMM} are respectively the maximum number of iterations for the GTRS-
 283 based and for the ADMM-based algorithms, Table 1 summarizes the worst-case computational complexity
 284 together with the average running time of the considered methods. The latter evaluation was performed
 285 with 100 Monte Carlo (MC) runs, for $N = 6$, $\sigma = 1$ dB, $\delta = 10$ dB, on a machine with the following

Algorithm 1 Pseudo-code for the Proposed VS Algorithm

Require: N : Number of anchors in the network
Require: \mathbf{a}_i : True anchor locations $i = 1, \dots, N$
Require: K : Number of measurement samples
Require: γ : Path loss exponent
Require: d_0 : Reference distance
Require: P_0 : Transmit power
Require: $P_{i,k}$: k -th RSS measurement sample at i -th anchor

- 1: **Initialization:** Set $\mathcal{M} = \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{H} = \{i : 1 \leq i \leq N\}$
- 2: Form circles centered at \mathbf{a}_i with radius d_i for $i = 1, \dots, N$
- 3: **for** $i = 1, \dots, N - 1$ **do**
- 4: **for** $j = i + 1, \dots, N$ **do**
- 5: **if** $c_i \cap c_j \neq \emptyset$ **then**
- 6: $q'_{ij}, q''_{ij} \leftarrow (4)$ //Find circle intersection points
- 7: **else**
- 8: $q'_{ij}, q''_{ij} \leftarrow (5)$ //Forge intersection points
- 9: **end if**
- 10: $H_{ij} \leftarrow (6)$ //Compute hyperplanes
- 11: $C_{ij}^{(l)} \subseteq H_{ij}^{(l)}$ and $C_{ij}^{(u)} \subseteq H_{ij}^{(u)}$ //Cluster in half spaces
- 12: **end for**
- 13: **end for**
- 14: $v_g \leftarrow (7)$ //Compute votes for cluster points
- 15: $\hat{\mathbf{x}} \leftarrow (10)$ //Estimate target's location
- 16: $\hat{\delta}_i \leftarrow (11)$ //Estimate attack intensity
- 17: $\hat{\sigma} \leftarrow (12)$ //Estimate noise STD
- 18: $\hat{p}_i \leftarrow (13)$ //Estimate expected genuine RSS value
- 19: **for** $i = 1, \dots, N$ **do**
- 20: **if** $P_i \in [\hat{P}_i - \hat{\sigma}, \hat{P}_i + \hat{\sigma}]$ **then**
- 21: $\mathcal{M} \leftarrow \mathcal{M} \cup \{i\}$ //Label anchor i as malicious
- 22: $\mathcal{H} \leftarrow \mathcal{H} \setminus \{i\}$ //Remove anchor i from honest ones
- 23: **end if**
- 24: **end for**
- 25: **Return:** $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and \mathcal{M}

286 characteristics: CPU: Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-1135G7 CPU @ 2.40 GHz, RAM: 16 GB, OS: Windows 11
 287 Home, running MATLAB R2016b.

288 Essentially, all considered methods involve matrix addition, multiplication and transpose operations,
 289 and the LC-GTRS in Tomic and Beko (2022) and SWLS in Mukhopadhyay et al. (2021) require matrix
 290 inversion. These operations come with certain computational costs associated with them (e.g., $\mathcal{O}(m^3)$ is
 291 the cost of matrix inversion, where m stands for the size of the square matrix). Nevertheless, one can note
 292 from the table that all considered algorithms have linear complexity in the dominant term, N . Regarding
 293 the complexity of the proposed VS method, its most expensive operation is the calculation of the votes
 294 in (7), where a series of matrix additions and multiplications is required in order to compute the projection
 295 of points of interest onto the hyperplane. However, dimensions of the matrices and vectors involved in
 296 these computations are fixed to $y \times y$ and y respectively, with y denoting the dimension of the space of
 297 interest (2-D or 3-D). Hence, although the operations in VS are computationally the least demanding, the
 298 proposed algorithm requires repeated actions (for each pair of anchors), which results in somewhat higher
 299 average running time than SWLS and R-GTRS. However, note that these actions could be done in parallel,
 300 so that the running time of VS is reduced significantly. Moreover, the GTRS-based and ADMM-based
 301 approaches require repeated actions, while LC-GTRS and LN-1E require two phases to obtain the final
 302 location estimation.

Table 1. Brief Summary of the Considered Algorithms

Algorithm	Complexity	Running Time (ms)	Type of attack	Additional requirements
VS in Section 3	$\binom{N}{2} \times \mathcal{O}(N)$	7	UC & C	No
LC-GTRS in Tomic and Beko (2022)	$2 \times \mathcal{O}(B_{\max} \times N)$	5	UC & C	No
SWLS in Mukhopadhyay et al. (2021)	$\mathcal{O}(N)$	1	UC	Knowledge about σ
LN-1E in Mukhopadhyay et al. (2021)	$2 \times \mathcal{O}(B_{\text{ADMM}} \times N)$	18	C	No
R-GTRS in Tomic and Beko (2024a)	$\mathcal{O}(B_{\max} \times N)$	1	UC & C	Knowledge about $\max\{ \delta_i \}$
WADMM in Tomic and Beko (2024b)	$\mathcal{O}(B_{\text{ADMM}} \times N)$	20	UC & C	No

303 4.2 Performance Analysis via Simulations

304 This section validates the performance of the considered algorithms in terms of localization accuracy
 305 and success of attacker detection through numerical simulations. All simulations disclose the results for N
 306 randomly deployed anchors and a single target (at a time), within a two-dimensional area of $25 \times 25 \text{ m}^2$
 307 with two malicious anchors. Moreover, anchors are randomly deployed $N_D = 1000$ times and, for each
 308 localization setting, two randomly chosen anchors are considered malicious $N_A = 50$ times.

309 The RSS measurements¹ were obtained through (1), where the transmit power at the target node is set to
 310 $P_0 = 15 \text{ dBm}$, the PLE is set at $\gamma = 3$, which corresponds to propagation in an urban area, and $K = 10$
 311 observation were considered. The main metric used to assess the localization performance is the root mean
 312 squared error (RMSE), $\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{MC} \frac{\|x_i - \hat{x}_i\|^2}{MC}}$ (m), where x_i and \hat{x}_i are, respectively, the true and the
 313 estimated target location in the i -th Monte Carlo run, i.e., $MC = N_D \times N_A$.

314 It is worth mentioning here that SWLS in Mukhopadhyay et al. (2021) requires tuning the detection
 315 threshold by studying an empirical parameter, ζ . By fine-tuning the empirical threshold in the considered
 316 settings, it was concluded that the best localization results for SWLS were obtained for $\zeta = 1.5$; thus, this
 317 value is adopted for SWLS in all presented simulations. Furthermore, R-GTRS in Tomic and Beko (2024a)
 318 requires knowledge on the magnitude of the attack intensity, i.e., $|\delta_i|$ in (1). The true value δ_i is given to
 319 R-GTRS in all presented simulations.

320 4.2.1 Uncoordinated Attacks

321 In a non-coordinated attack, the attack intensity in (1) is chosen according to

$$\delta_i = \begin{cases} 0, & i \in \mathcal{H} \\ \delta, & i \in \mathcal{M} \end{cases},$$

322 where δ (dB) is defined below for each scenario.

323 Fig. 4 illustrates RMSE (m) versus δ (dB) comparison of the considered approaches in an uncoordinated
 324 attack scenario with two malicious anchors for different values of N and σ (dB). As expected, the figure
 325 clearly shows that the performance of all methods degrades with the increase of $|\delta|$ (dB). Likewise, it
 326 shows a trend that all methods benefit from the increase of N and suffer from the increase of σ (dB). From
 327 Fig. 4, one can see that the proposed solution outperforms the existing ones for medium-to-high $|\delta|$ (dB),
 328 whereas R-GTRS exhibits superior performance for low $|\delta|$ (dB). Nevertheless, R-GTRS suffers significant
 329 performance degradation for high $|\delta|$ (dB), making it unusable in these settings. This behavior most likely

¹ Note that this work considers PLE and the transmit power known a priori. This might not be the case in practice, so these parameters might not be (perfectly) known beforehand. Considering these parameters not known might be an interesting direction for future work.

Figure 4a. $N = 6$ and $\sigma = 1$ (dB)

Figure 4b. $N = 7$ and $\sigma = 1$ (dB)

Figure 4c. $N = 7$ and $\sigma = 3$ (dB)

Figure 4. RMSE (m) versus δ (dB) in an uncoordinated attack scenario.

occurs due to a high dis-balance between the number of genuine and malicious anchors in the considered scenario, causing R-GTRS to erroneously penalize the genuine anchors instead of the malicious ones. This is particularly noticeable when $|\delta|$ is relatively high, causing significant difference in malicious and genuine measurements and tricking R-GTRS to mistakenly penalize more the genuine anchors, thus favoring the malicious ones and resulting in higher performance loss. Hence, although it is a robust min-max approach that is conceived for the worst-case scenario (it assumes that all anchors malicious initially), R-GTRS method experiences difficulties in *lighter* and *milder* settings.

Fig. 5 illustrates different detection rates versus δ (dB) comparison of the considered approaches in an uncoordinated attack scenario with two malicious anchors for different values of N and σ (dB). In order to show the stability of the detection results, 95% Wilson binomial CI Wilson (1927) is employed to provide accurate coverage for finite sample sizes. In this way, each detection outcome is a Bernoulli process, with the correct detection corresponding to success, and all other outcomes (false and no detection) are treated as failure. The CI is calculated as

$$CI = \left[\frac{P_{CD} + \frac{z^2}{2MC|\mathcal{M}|} - z\sqrt{\frac{P_{CD}(1-P_{CD})}{MC|\mathcal{M}|} + \frac{z^2}{4(MC|\mathcal{M}|)^2}}}{1 + \frac{z^2}{MC|\mathcal{M}|}}, \frac{P_{CD} + \frac{z^2}{2MC|\mathcal{M}|} + z\sqrt{\frac{P_{CD}(1-P_{CD})}{MC|\mathcal{M}|} + \frac{z^2}{4(MC|\mathcal{M}|)^2}}}{1 + \frac{z^2}{MC|\mathcal{M}|}} \right], \quad (14)$$

with P_{CD} denoting the empirical correct detection rate, MC and $|\mathcal{M}|$ respectively being the number of Monte Carlo runs and the number of attackers, and z representing the standard normal quantile ($z = 1.96$)

Figure 5a. $N = 6$ and $\sigma = 1$ (dB)

Figure 5b. $N = 7$ and $\sigma = 1$ (dB)

Figure 5c. $N = 7$ and $\sigma = 3$ (dB)

Figure 5. Detection rates versus δ (dB) in an uncoordinated attack scenario.

345 for 95% confidence interval). Fig. 5 corroborates the effectiveness of the proposed detection scheme and
 346 confirms the superiority of the proposed approach for high $|\delta|$ (dB). The latter claim can be explained by
 347 the robustness of the proposed approach to high $|\delta|$ (dB) in terms of localization performance, since the
 348 location estimate of VS is exploited for detection, and having better localization estimate can naturally lead
 349 better detection performance (if used in a correct manner). Finally, it is worth mentioning that the detection
 350 of SWLS is poor in general, which suggest that its hyper-parameter ζ might need more fine-tuning (even
 351 though $\zeta = 1.5$ resulted in the best localization performance).

352 Fig. 6 illustrates the cumulative distribution function (CDF) versus localization error (LE) in the consi-
 353 dered uncoordinated scenario, when $N = 7$, $\delta = 7$ (dB) and $\sigma = 1$ (dB). The LE in the i -th MC run is
 354 defined as $LE_i = \|\mathbf{x}_i - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i\|$. The figure shows that the proposed scheme and LC-GTRS exhibit similar
 355 performance which is clearly superior over the remaining existing ones. For instance, the former two
 356 solutions have a median of $LE \approx 0.4$ (m), whereas the best of the remaining ones exhibits a median of
 357 $LE \approx 4.5$ (m).

358 4.2.2 Coordinated Attacks

359 In a coordinated attack, \mathbf{x}_{att} in (2) is obtained by choosing a random point on a circle centered at the true
 360 target's location with radius δ , i.e., $\mathbf{x}_{att} = \mathbf{x} + \delta[\cos \theta, \sin \theta]^T$, where θ is a random angle chosen from a
 361 uniform distribution from the interval $[0, 2\pi]$.

362 Fig. 7 illustrates RMSE (m) versus δ (dB) comparison of the considered approaches in a coordinated attack
 363 scenario with two malicious anchors for different values of N and σ (dB). Similar as in the uncoordinated

Figure 6. CDF versus LE (m) in an uncoordinated attack scenario, when $N = 7$ and $\sigma = 1$ (dB).

Figure 7a. $N = 6$ and $\sigma = 1$ (dB)

Figure 7b. $N = 7$ and $\sigma = 1$ (dB)

Figure 7c. $N = 7$ and $\sigma = 3$ (dB)

Figure 7. RMSE (m) versus δ (dB) in a coordinated attack scenario.

364 scenario, Fig. 7 exhibits superior performance of the proposed solution for medium-to-high $|\delta|$ (dB), being
 365 R-GTRS and LN-1E its only competitors for low $|\delta|$ (dB). This result suggests that these two methods
 366 might be somewhat more robust to noise, since low $|\delta|$ (dB) can be seen as noise corruption. Still, the gain
 367 that the new method achieves for high $|\delta|$ (dB) clearly compensates this behavior.

368 Fig. 8 illustrates different detection rates versus δ (dB) comparison of the considered approaches in a
 369 coordinated attack scenario with two malicious anchors for different values of N and σ (dB). As foreseen,
 370 (correct) detection performance of all methods degrades with the increase of σ (dB). This is explained by
 371 the fact that higher noise power gives attackers more room to disguise their malicious deeds within the

Figure 8a. $N = 6$ and $\sigma = 1$ (dB)

Figure 8b. $N = 7$ and $\sigma = 1$ (dB)

Figure 8c. $N = 7$ and $\sigma = 3$ (dB)

Figure 8. Detection rates versus δ (dB) in a coordinated attack scenario.

Figure 9. CDF versus LE (m) in a coordinated attack scenario, when $N = 7$ and $\sigma = 1$ (dB).

372 noise, aggravating the detection process. This is particularly discernible for all methods in the interval
 373 $0 < \frac{|\delta|}{\sigma} \leq 2$. Nonetheless, the proposed scheme significantly outperforms the existing ones in terms of
 374 attacker detection in general.

375 Fig. 9 illustrates the cumulative distribution function (CDF) versus localization error (LE) in the con-
 376 sidered coordinated scenario, when $N = 7$, $\delta = 7$ (dB) and $\sigma = 1$ (dB). Fig. 9 shows that the proposed
 377 scheme and LC-GTRS have almost identical performance which is clearly superior over the remaining
 378 existing ones. For instance, the former two solutions have a median of $LE \approx 0.4$ (m), whereas the best of
 379 the remaining ones exhibits a median of $LE \approx 3$ (m).

Figure 10a. RMSE (m) vs. $|\mathcal{M}|$ in the considered uncoordinated scenario

Figure 10b. Detection rates vs. $|\mathcal{M}|$ in the considered uncoordinated scenario

Figure 10c. RMSE (m) vs. $|\mathcal{M}|$ in the considered coordinated scenario

Figure 10d. Detection rates vs. $|\mathcal{M}|$ in the considered coordinated scenario

Figure 10. Performance comparison of the considered methods for different number of attackers, $|\mathcal{M}|$, when $N = 20$, $\delta = 10$ (dB), $\sigma = 3$ (dB), $K = 10$, $N_A = 50$, $N_D = 1000$.

380 To finish off the analysis via computer simulations, Fig. 10 illustrates the performance comparison in
 381 the considered uncoordinated and coordinated attack scenarios, when $N = 20$, $\delta = 10$ (dB), $\sigma = 3$ (dB),
 382 $K = 10$, where $|\mathcal{M}|$ attackers were randomly chosen $N_A = 50$ times in each of $N_D = 1000$ random
 383 deployments of all nodes. The figure illustrates general superiority of the proposed VS in both uncoordinated
 384 and coordinated attack scenarios. Only R-GTRS manages to provide better results in uncoordinated attack
 385 scenario when half of the anchors are malicious. This is not surprising, since the R-GTRS method is a
 386 robust min-max approach that is conceived for the worst-case scenario, but experiences difficulties in
 387 lighter and milder settings. Similarly, the proposed detection scheme outperforms the existing ones in both
 388 scenarios in general, achieving around 90% of correct attacker detection in the considered uncoordinated
 389 attack scenarios when at least 30% of anchors are malicious.

390 4.3 Performance Analysis via Experimental Measurements

391 This section validates the performance of the considered algorithms in terms of localization accuracy
 392 and success of attacker detection through experimental measurements. The considered experimental
 393 configuration is illustrated in Fig. 11. In all experiments, $K = 50$ was considered to localize a single target
 394 at a time, in the presence of two malicious anchors. Moreover, two randomly chosen anchors in each run

Figure 11. Real-world experimental set up under consideration: blue circles and black squares respectively denote the true target and anchor locations. The data set is a courtesy of our colleagues from Computer Science department at Rutgers University Niculescu and Nath (2004).

Figure 12. RMSE (m) versus δ (dB) in the considered experimental uncoordinated attack scenario, for $N_A = 100$.

395 out of $N_A = 100$ runs are considered malicious, and their spoofing attacks were generated by simply
 396 injecting a value into the acquired experimental measurements.

397 4.3.1 Uncoordinated Attacks

398 Fig. 12 illustrates RMSE (m) versus δ (dB) comparison of the considered approaches in the experimental
 399 uncoordinated attack scenario with two malicious anchors. The figure exhibits that only R-GTRS performs
 400 better than the proposed scheme for low-to-medium δ (dB), whereas for high attack intensities (e.g.,
 401 $|\delta| \geq 7$), both methods exhibit similar performance. Nevertheless, it is worth remembering that R-GTRS
 402 requires additional knowledge about the maximum attack intensity, which is unlikely to be perfectly
 403 available beforehand in practice.

404 Fig. 13 illustrates detection rates versus δ (dB) comparison of the considered approaches in the experi-
 405 mental uncoordinated attack scenario with two malicious anchors. Fig. 13 shows that the achieved detection
 406 rates are significantly lower than the ones from the simulations, but this is expected given various obstacles,
 407 anisotropies and other phenomena that were not considered in simulations. Even so, the results indicate
 408 that the proposed detection scheme works well in practice, which is corroborated by the fact that its results
 409 match the best existing ones, LC-GTRS in this case, and go up to $\approx 34\%$.

410 4.3.2 Coordinated Attacks

411 Fig. 14 illustrates RMSE (m) versus δ (dB) comparison of the considered approaches in the experimental
 412 coordinated attack scenario with two malicious anchors. Similar as in the uncoordinated case, only R-GTRS
 413 performs better than the proposed scheme for low-to-medium δ (dB), whereas for high attack intensities
 414 (e.g., $|\delta| \geq 7$), the proposed approach exhibits the best performance.

Figure 13. Detection rates versus δ (dB) in the considered experimental uncoordinated attack scenario, for $N_A = 100$.

Figure 14. RMSE (m) versus δ (dB) in the considered experimental coordinated attack scenario, for $N_A = 100$.

Figure 15. Detection rates versus δ (dB) in the considered experimental coordinated attack scenario, for $N_A = 100$.

415 Fig. 15 illustrates detection rates versus δ (dB) comparison of the considered approaches in the experi-
 416 mental coordinated attack scenario with two malicious anchors. Naturally, the figure shows a drop in the
 417 detection rates when compared with the ones in the simulations. Again, the proposed detection scheme is
 418 corroborated in practice, matching the performance of the best existing one, and goes up to $\approx 30\%$.

419 **4.4 Discussion**

420 While the proposed solution outperforms existing methods in localization and detection for medium-to-
 421 high attack intensity, some limitations and parameter choices are worth discussing. Certain parameters are
 422 fixed, such as the number of points of interest set to $N - 1$ for localization and the confidence interval for

Figure 16a. Uncoordinated attacks

Figure 16b. Coordinated attacks

Figure 16. $ARMSE_{\delta}$ versus δ (dB) in the considered experimental scenario, for $N_A = 100$.

423 attacker detection set within one estimated noise standard deviation. The rationale for using $N - 1$ points
 424 is that not all N intersection points are necessary, as some may be affected by attacks or excessive noise.
 425 For smaller N , trimming unnecessary points improves accuracy. The confidence interval choice balances
 426 false detection (if too narrow) and missed detection (if too wide), with one standard deviation offering
 427 a reasonable trade-off. Although these parameters could be fine-tuned for different scenarios, numerical
 428 results indicate that the chosen values work well within the considered settings.

429 The proposed approach assigns beliefs (votes) to each intersection point, but under high noise or unfavo-
 430 rable attack coordination, it may mistakenly remove a genuine point, potentially impacting localization
 431 accuracy. However, numerical results confirm that such occurrences are infrequent and do not significantly
 432 degrade performance. While the final detection output is a binary decision (genuine or malicious anchor),
 433 this classification is solely for detection purposes and does not influence localization refinement. Like
 434 existing methods, the approach requires at least 50 % of anchors to be non-compromised, particularly in
 435 coordinated attacks, as a malicious majority would easily manipulate localization. A unique aspect of the
 436 method is its ability to generate points of interest even when anchor circles do not intersect. In extreme
 437 cases, all points might need to be fabricated, leading to inaccurate clusters. However, this scenario poses a
 438 challenge for all existing methods, as they inherently rely on intersection points for localization.

439 Although not all considered methods estimate the attack intensity directly in their detection procedure,
 440 one can obtain this estimate as explained here in (11). Hence, Fig. 16 illustrates the average RMSE of
 441 $\delta = [\delta_i]^T$ ($ARMSE_{\delta}$) in (dB) versus δ (dB) in the considered experimental uncoordinated attack scenario,
 442 Fig.16a, and the considered experimental coordinated attack scenario, Fig.16b, for $N_A = 100$. The figure
 443 shows that none of the considered approaches accomplishes an error below 7 (dB), which is due to the
 444 complexity of the scenario. Still, the proposed scheme exhibits a fairly good, but in general not the best,
 445 estimation performance, indicating that this estimation is not a prerequisite for high detection rate, which
 446 is somewhat intuitive. Finally, it is worth mentioning that the results of LN-1E are around 22 dBs in the
 447 considered setting, and are thus cut off for a better overview.

5 CONCLUSIONS

448 This work advances target localization in randomly deployed WSNs under both uncoordinated and coordi-
 449 nated spoofing attacks by introducing a novel geometric approach for accurate localization and attacker

450 detection. The method estimates the target's location using intersection points of anchor pairs, applying
451 a VS and WCM, followed by attacker detection via confidence intervals. Unlike traditional methods, it
452 employs soft detection decisions, assigning beliefs (votes) instead of binary classifications. These votes are
453 converted into probabilities and used as WCM weights for refined localization. Potential attack intensities
454 are estimated using an ML criterion, with final detection based on confidence intervals. Performance
455 evaluation in terms of localization accuracy, detection rate, and computational complexity shows that
456 the method achieves near-perfect detection when the attack intensity-to-noise ratio is sufficiently high.
457 Although detection rate decreases as this ratio lowers, the proposed approach consistently outperforms
458 existing methods in both detection performance and localization accuracy, reducing localization error by at
459 least 30 % across various scenarios. Additionally, the VS-based solution operates efficiently, with a runtime
460 of just a few milliseconds.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

461 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
462 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

463 All authors contributed equally.

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